

EU FOREIGN POLICY AND COSMOPOLITAN CITIZENSHIP*

Keywords: *Supranational Political Economy, European Integration, Federalism, Cosmopolitanism.*

Ключевые слова: *наднациональная политическая экономия, европейская интеграция, федерализм, космополитизм.*

**Расширенная аннотация статьи
на русском языке¹**

В своем первом выступлении в Европейском парламенте Урсула фон дер Ляйен сказала: «Миру нужно наше лидерство... Мы можем сформировать лучший миропорядок... Я имею в виду именно эту геополитическую комиссию». Глава внешней политики ЕС Хосеп Боррелл после пандемического кризиса заявил: «Генеральный секретарь ООН Антонио Гутерриш и я поняли, что мы не выйдем из кризиса без сильных и скоординированных действий между Китаем, США и Европой» (6 мая 2020 г.)».

Мы должны признать, что угрозы будущему человечества, носят глобальный, а не только национальный характер. Главная из них - это коллапс биосферы, вызванный разрушением

природной среды из-за безудержного роста промышленности и массового роста населения Земли. Старая модель развития больше не является устойчивой на планете с ограниченными ресурсами. Что касается военной безопасности граждан, международная ситуация сейчас очень опасна. Договоры о разоружении, положившие конец холодной войне, были отменены или отмирают. Международными организациями, созданными после Второй мировой войны для установления мирного миропорядка, в том числе Организацией Объединенных Наций и ее специализированными учреждениями, все больше пренебрегают.

Новый международный порядок должен строиться на новых принципах и новых институтах. После Первой мировой войны США предложили Лигу Наций как средство достижения «международной демократии»; Советский Союз предложил Коммунистический

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Интернационал, чтобы способствовать мировой коммунистической революции. Сегодня ЕС считается слабым международным субъектом по сравнению с великими державами, такими как США, Китай, Россия и Индия, и действительно, это не военная держава. Однако в 2012 году ЕС получил Нобелевскую премию, потому что «помог преобразовать большую часть Европы из континента войны в континент мира». То же самое может быть достигнуто во всем мире, если ЕС сумеет продемонстрировать, что нынешний всплеск национализма можно преодолеть путем реформирования и укрепления многосторонности в ООН. Европейское гражданство — это новая модель наднациональной интеграции и космополитическое гражданство — это путь к достижению мирного мирового порядка. Гражданство ЕС дополняет национальное гражданство, и признает права, свободы и принципы, изложенные в Хартии основных прав. Почему для людей всего мира космополитическое гражданство должно быть химерой?

В данной статье рассматриваются два геополитических проекта, которые ЕС мог бы разработать: а) с Африканским союзом для совместного партнерства: мы предлагаем обеспечивать регулярные миграционные потоки, чтобы прибывающие мигранты могли въехать на территорию ЕС, независимо от пересекаемой национальной границы; и б) с Россией для построения Общего европейского дома. В статье предлагается Новый атлантический пакт, реализующий четыре свободы, которые были бы краеугольным камнем европейской интеграции: свобода передвижения товаров, людей, услуг и капитала. Более того, в документе также исследуются основные направления политики, которую ЕС может проводить в рамках

ООН, чтобы построить мирное глобальное управление для устойчивого развития планеты и обеспечения соблюдения прав человека в соответствии со Всеобщей декларацией прав человека (1948 г.). В статье рассматривается реформа международной торговой системы (ВТО), реформа международной валютной системы (выпуск СДР МВФ в качестве новых международных денег) и предлагается создание Мирового налогового управления, которое будет управлять мировым регистром благосостояния граждан и консолидированной прибылью всех транснациональных компаний.

Realism and values in international politics

In international politics the situation tends to swing between affirming values and defending one's own interests, national interests first and foremost: in some periods certain values and principles are championed, such as free trade, democracy, socialism and peace, while in others the pursuit of national interests by means of power politics prevails, as happened in the first half of the last century. If we consider "the short century" - the time period proposed by Hobsbawm - immediately after the end of the First World War two opposing conceptions of international politics emerged: the American view, which proposed the League of Nations, to make the world a safe place for democracy, and that of the Communist International, which framed the Soviet Union as the forerunner for the emancipation of the world's proletariat. After the Second World War, these two conceptions shaped the ideological conflict between the two superpowers.

The thirty years since the Cold War have seen firstly the breakdown of the Soviet Union, then the slow decline of the US as a superpower. We are now witnessing

the birth of a new multipolar world order, with the rise of major new powers, the most important of which is China. Yet it is impossible to say whether we are heading into a period of unstoppable disorder, or experiencing a transition, and if so, what to? The 2020 pandemic has highlighted both the presence of international solidarity, with doctors and researchers around the world doing their utmost to fight the virus, and signs of worrying rivalries between national governments, which have taken advantage of the emergency to increase their power both domestically and internationally.

We need to identify a realistic way forward. This is the most difficult task for politics, because the political system is not just national, but global. A way forward corresponds to an idea of progress, but today, what party, and what government is capable of indicating a path towards a world order better than the existing one, for the progress of humanity? Anne-Marie Slaughter makes an important point: that while the governments of today invest huge amounts of money and human resources in guaranteeing national security, the greatest threats to humanity's future are no longer just those coming from other powers. "Those efforts have largely failed — Slaughter says — and it is time to try a new approach. Instead of widening our definition of national security, we need to start *narrowing* it. That means distinguishing national security from global security and putting military security in its place alongside many other equally important but distinct priorities" (Slaughter 2020; original italics).

We need to acknowledge that the threats jeopardizing the future of humanity are global, not just national. The main one is the collapse of the biosphere, caused by the destruction of the natural environment due to the unfettered expan-

sion of industry and the massive increase in the world's population. The old model of development is no longer sustainable on a planet with limited resources. The pandemic is a revealing but partial episode. If national governments do not act, today's young people risk facing the angry backlash of a planet in its death throes. Yet international terrorism, cyber security, international migration, the unchecked power of international finance, and international production chains are all variables that lie beyond the control of national governments. National sovereignty can now only be defended by endowing supranational institutions with sufficient powers to supply global public goods, such as peaceful cooperation, public health, monetary stability, the regulation of international trade and collective security.

From this perspective, as we will try to show, a crucial role can be played by the European Union (EU). The European Union is not viewed as a world power because it does not have its own army, but its history proves how nations which were once enemies have succeeded in overcoming the divisions of the past and launching an economic and political cooperation that has transformed the European continent "from a continent of war to a continent of peace", as stated in the motivation for the Nobel Peace Prize awarded to the EU in 2012. The EU therefore has a vital interest in pursuing its own foreign policy, which has the primary objective of returning to the rules of multilateralism that characterized the period from the end of the Second World War to that of the Cold War. Since then, the ongoing decline of US hegemony and the emergence of major new powers have paved the way for the return of nationalism as the dominant principle of international politics. The EU shows that national peoples can understand the distinction between national sovereignty,

which does not admit any external constraints, and national independence, which is compatible with interdependence, and loyal, peaceful collaboration with other national peoples, through the transfer of some powers - such as the regulation of a common market, monetary policy and part of fiscal powers - to supranational institutions.

Over a period of 70 years, the EU has managed to create a system of integration not only among governments, but also among citizens, today symbolized by European citizenship: young people can study or work in any other country in the Union. The rights of European citizens are protected by the EU *Charter of Fundamental Rights*. This is a model of society and citizenship that the EU can offer up to other peoples, as the US and the Soviet Union did after the First World War with democracy and socialism respectively. Cosmopolitan citizenship should be seen as a very long-term goal. There are undoubtedly intermediate stages and challenging obstacles to overcome. It could also be argued that cosmopolitan citizenship is a "utopian" goal. It is a reasonable objection, but, as I have tried to show (Montani 2020), every political ideology - I am referring to the traditional ideologies: liberalism, democracy, socialism and nationalism - contains a utopian aspect.

But utopia does not just mean imaginative or unrealistic thinking; utopia can also indicate a long-term, positive project, as opposed to a negative project, that is, a dystopia. Cosmopolitan citizenship is a positive utopia, because a cosmopolitan society already exists (for example, in the worlds of scientific research, literature, business, finance and fashion), and migrants are citizens of the world in search of a homeland to welcome them. Every traditional ideology contains a positive utopia, albeit difficult to identify. Cosmopolitan

citizenship incorporates the fundamental ideals of traditional ideologies, with the exception of nationalism. The latter, after its embryonic phase in the first half of the nineteenth century, when the ideals of the self-determination of peoples and their independence fuelled the struggle for national unifications (as happened in Italy, Germany and, later, India, China, Vietnam etc.), turned out to be the ideological cover for power politics, oppression, wars of extermination and racism, until Nazi-fascism was defeated. Nationalism is now a dystopia.

The issue I want to address in this essay is that of how, in the coming years, the EU can contribute to building some important, albeit partial, institutions on the path to cosmopolitan citizenship. Before presenting her strategy for a European Green Deal, the President of the European Commission Ursula von der Leyen, in her speech to the European Parliament, said: "The world needs our leadership ... We can be the shapers of a better global order ... This is the geopolitical Commission that I have in mind". As a contribution to this, I would therefore like to present some proposals for a European foreign policy which addresses: a) cooperation between the EU and the African Union; b) relations between the EU and Russia, and c) some ideas for global governance, with the aim of reviving peaceful multilateral cooperation in the UN and its agencies.

Cooperation between the African Union and the European Union

Euro-African cooperation began in the late 1950s, after the EEC Treaty was adopted, with the European Development Fund. In 1969, the Yaoundé Convention between the EEC and Union Africaine et Malgache was approved. In 1975, after the United Kingdom joined the EEC, and thanks to the creation of the OUA (Organi-

zation of African Unity), the Lomé Convention was adopted, between the EU and 46 ACP countries (Africa, Caribbean, Pacific). The Convention marked a turning point in the panorama of international aid. In the context of the UN, attempts by developing countries to forge a New International Economic Order (NIEO), with mechanisms to support the prices of raw materials exported from non-industrialized countries (*Trade not Aid*), had failed. The Lomé Convention, on the other hand, introduced these mechanisms: first the Stabex, for agricultural products, and later the Sysmin, for mineral products. In addition, over time, the Convention was added to with rules safeguarding human rights and supporting non-discrimination, women's empowerment, education, the protection of democratic institutions and decentralized cooperation (with NGOs).

By 2000 there were 77 countries in the ACP: 48 in Africa, 15 in the Caribbean and 14 in the Pacific. But the global scenario had changed dramatically since the end of the Cold War. In 1994, the WTO was founded in Marrakesh. In the new world order, with global freedom of trade, a number of emerging countries protested about the favourable treatment enjoyed by the countries of the Lomé Convention. In addition, the UN had approved its Millennium Goals, which provided a coherent set of policy indications for sustainable development on a global scale. To replace the Lomé Convention, the Cotonou Agreement between the EU and the ACP countries was signed in 2000, valid for a period of twenty years and renewable every five. Its aim was to encourage the inclusion of ACP countries in the global economy, and to make them competitive by overcoming tariff discrimination and opening up to international investments, whose flows now exceeded those of public development aid. Furthermore,

in 2000 in Lomé, 53 African countries decided to found the African Union, whose institutions are very similar to European ones. There is a Union Assembly, where the heads of state and government sit, and a Council of Ministers, which discusses common policies. There is a Pan-African Parliament, which has five representatives for each of the 53 African countries, and lastly there is a Commission, which acts as the Union's executive secretariat, and a Court of Justice.

In this context it is easy to understand the significance of the meeting that took place in Addis Ababa on 29th February 2020 between the African Commission and the European Commission, Commission-to-Commission (C2C): a supranational meeting between two supranational institutions. The *Joint Communiqué* is full of common initiatives, as follows: "The C2C is a building block of an enhanced partnership; the European Commission welcomed the entry into force of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) and reiterated its support for an enhanced observer status for the African Union at the WTO; the C2C took cognizance of the challenges posed by climate change and support Agenda 2063 (for AU) and Agenda 2030 (for EU); support an efficient African continental transport network and a Single Air Transport Market; they agreed on implementing the 2018 AU-EU Memorandum of Understanding on Peace, Security and Governance and the association of the UN as relevant; both parties recognized the strategic significance of the revitalised AU Peace Fund and the EU Peace Facility; they support the joint framework for strengthened Continent-to-Continent dialogue on migration and mobility and agreed on priority in education, science, technology, innovation and skills development, notably the AU-EU Skills for Youth Employability Programme".

I do not have room here to comment on all the initiatives: my more limited focus is on migration from Africa to Europe and how it relates to cosmopolitan citizenship. Migration flows are a serious issue for both Unions. In an in-depth examination of the demographics of the two continents, Stephen Smith notes: "Today, the European Union (including the UK) has some 510 million inhabitants, while there are 1.3 billion people in neighbouring Africa. ... As the population of Europe continues to age, Africa's demographic will continue to trend in the opposite direction. By 2050, two-thirds of Africans will be less than thirty years old" (Smith 2019; 8). Migration flows from Africa to the EU are therefore a structural problem that must be regulated with forward-looking policies. Young people in Africa leave the countryside for the city, to be free from oppressive family ties, then from the city they decide to seek their fortune in industrialized countries. At the end of his analysis Smith asserts: "The massive migration of Africans to Europe is in the interest of neither Young Africa nor the Old Continent. For Europe, ... the decline in its working population will almost certainly be a net gain for Europe, not a loss. Africa, on the other end, has far more to lose than to win from the large-scale 'exportation' of its youth" (Smith 2019: 165). Alongside these considerations, there is the alarming prospect of global warming, which is sparking a surge of "ecological migrants". To date, the 2015 Paris Agreements have largely been ignored by national governments, and Africa is undoubtedly the continent set to suffer most from the effects of the climate emergency.

AU-EU cooperation enables the issue of emigration to be addressed with structural policies, that is within a political-juridical-economic framework, with the aim of reconciling the needs of the two continents long term. The Dublin Conven-

tion, which was first formulated in 1990, when migration flows to Europe were manageable, decrees that the first European country migrants or refugees arrive in is responsible for taking them in. With massive flows, this system is unsustainable, especially for Mediterranean countries such as Greece, Italy, Spain, Malta and Cyprus, those most exposed to flows from Africa and the Middle East. Closing European borders has favoured the trafficking of migrants and the creation of detention hotspots, with uncertain assistance from neighbouring countries - which has to be paid for - as happened with the agreements between the EU and Turkey in 2016, and, lastly the forced deportation of irregular immigrants. The EU's immigration policy cannot be borne by its southern member states alone: the burden must be shared, as applies to all issues concerning external relations.

Here I would like to outline some proposals for the creation of legal migration channels that could be considered by the two Commissions, C2C. Legal channels are the real remedy for illegal ones. In recent years, a distinction has been made between refugees (with regard to refugees, see Archibugi et al, 2019) and economic migrants, but this is increasingly difficult to maintain when it comes to the new migration flows generated by the collapse of the biosphere. The proposals must take both problems into account, in the knowledge that the phenomenon of migration presents significant political aspects, as it is often negatively viewed by part of the population and the political establishment hostile to immigrants being integrated into national society, but also positive aspects, especially on the economic front, because - if well regulated - immigration can contribute to the income of both the host country and that of the migrants' origin (The Economist, 2019). I will focus on

the issue of citizenship, because the only way for the EU to solve most of the difficulties, errors and injustices created by the Dublin rules is by using well-identified channels for legal transits managed jointly by the two Commissions, C2C. The African countries of origin must take responsibility for determining how many and which citizens can access the system of recruitment, transit and reception, and European countries must come to an agreement on how many people can be accepted into the EU and how to ensure that immigrants are properly integrated into European society. In parallel, effective cooperation agreements must be created for education and university exchanges, as well as for scientific research. Young Africans should be encouraged to study in their own countries or come to Europe for limited periods of time to study or work.

The crucial principle behind the proposal aimed at ensuring regular migration flows is that the incoming migrant is entering EU territory, regardless of the national border crossed. If migrants cross the European border through a legal channel their final destination will be decided on before their departure, and accepted by them. Migrants who enter illegally will be repatriated (if they come from one of the countries participating in the agreement) or temporarily hosted in a hosting centre. The European system of integration should be based on something that all EU member countries possess, that is, autonomous local governments (city, province, region). Currently the main obstacles to a common immigration policy are the different countries' differing approaches to receiving immigrants, and the differing legal approach to the issue of citizenship - *ius soli* or *ius sanguinis* - largely applied in varying ways in each nation. For years these two elements have been a bone of contention among European countries, leading them

to reject the quota system proposed by the European Commission. To overcome this resistance and enable immigrants to circulate freely in the Schengen area, just like all European citizens, the EU has to undertake a major, but not impossible, reform of national legal systems with regard to citizenship, which should be harmonized. Rainer Bauböck proposes: "coordinating access to EU and national citizenship through some common basic standards for *ius soli* and *ius sanguinis*, for naturalization, renunciation, and withdrawal. Allowing the CJEU to expand the scope of EU citizenship rights" (Bauböck 2014; 762).

This first reform should be followed by the introduction of an effective system of integration in European society, at all levels. Upon entering the EU, immigrants will receive local citizenship (*jus domicilii*) or citizenship of their area of residence (at city, provincial or regional level, depending on what the host country has decided). The local level is where it will be easier for newcomers to find a favourable social environment, because almost all social services are provided by local authorities. Their rights will be guaranteed by the EU *Charter of Fundamental Rights*, on a par with other European citizens. This is a new status, both legally and politically, because immigrants will have the right to vote in local elections. Article 9 of the Lisbon Treaty states that: "Anyone who is a citizen of a member state is a citizen of the Union". This proposed local 'citizenship' will not enable immigrants to vote in European elections, until they acquire national citizenship too. On a national level, integration will be pursued according to the rules established by each national government.

These proposals will not solve the problem of national quotas in the European planning of annual flows of immigrants. Yet long-term planning will be facilitated by the involvement of local authorities,

which can contribute, in line with their economic needs and political sensitivities, to ensuring the integration of immigrants into European civil society. It should also be considered that, with free circulation in the Schengen area, relations between families and linguistic communities - not necessarily residing in the same place - are facilitated. It may therefore be the case that a family accepted by one EU country has children who apply for citizenship of other European countries, for work or other reasons.

These proposals implement the principles in article 21 of the Lisbon Treaty - respect for human dignity, fundamental freedoms, equality and solidarity - which to date have not been upheld by the Dublin regulation and European immigration policies. They also strengthen the political role of the two commissions and the unity of the two continents. As Nadia Urbinati argues: "Restrictions on asylum, difficulty of integration, detention in host centres located on Europe's borders and in airports, and lastly expulsion are the strategies that qualify European citizenship as a new form of national citizenship rather than a supranational or even cosmopolitan citizenship, as envisaged in the idealized view of the Lisbon Treaty" (Urbinati 2015; 86).

EU-Russia relations and the Common European Home

The end of the Cold War forced the EU and Russia to seek a new equilibrium. After a period of peaceful cooperation, tensions arose in 2014, after Russia annexed Crimea. As Russia aspires to being a world power, it is not entirely correct to frame the crisis between the EU and Russia as a geopolitical one: a number of global aspects come into play, and the security of both is at stake.

The proposal I intend to discuss here is the "Common European Home", which

Mikhail Gorbachev illustrated in two speeches in Prague and Warsaw in 1987. At that time the topic was security and disarmament in Europe. In his *Memoirs*, Gorbachev writes: "We had to break out of the vicious circle of mistrust and finally begin the process of conventional disarmament. In a speech to the Polish parliament, I suggested a kind of 'European Reykjavik' — a summit meeting of all European leaders, in the hope that we could achieve a similar breakthrough in European affairs as we had in Soviet-American relations during our meeting with Ronald Reagan in Iceland" (Gorbachev 1996; 557). The question is formulated in imprecise terms, but it clearly regards NATO and the issue of security on the Continent, including the USSR - something that emerged repeatedly, especially on the occasion of German reunification. In July 1990, Gorbachev and Kohl discussed the conditions for unification, including, "the non-extension of the NATO military structure onto East German territory" (p. 689). Lastly, after the breakup of the USSR, he notes: "The increasing tendency for confrontation between Russia and the West over NATO's planned expansion prompted me to remind Western politicians that during the negotiations on the unification of Germany they gave assurances that NATO would not extend its zone of operation to the east. ... the policy of enlarging NATO will be considered in Russia as an attempt to isolate it" (p. 871).

The issues raised by the idea of a Common European Home should be recalled because they are crucial in terms of understanding the current security problems in Europe; problems that cannot be solved without a wide-ranging, fair agreement between the EU and Russia. To this end, it is useful to remember that the EU too has made proposals similar to those of Gorbachev. Jacques Delors, President of the European Commission, remembers

it clearly: as the issue of European security could not be ignored, Delors recalls, “I proposed a simple scheme, in the spirit of the proposal made by François Mitterrand on 31 December 1989, with his European Confederation” (Delors 1994; 262). The European Confederation was intended to bring together all the European countries to guarantee peace, security and the free movement of people and goods. When it comes to the issue of extending the European Union in the east, Delors notes that it was not possible to ask Russia to join the EU, because that would generate an imbalance among EU members, but by the same token it was also not possible to ask all its neighbours to join. “The countries of the former Soviet Union will be our associates. On the condition of recognizing Russia as a great world power ... and offering it a close partnership in economic and commercial matters. We need to bear Russian sensitivities in mind... the Russians opposed Poland’s accession to the Atlantic Alliance ... Greater Europe stops at the borders of the CIS (Community of Independent States), but including the Baltic countries by our side is historically indisputable” (pp. 268-9). At that time the CIS states included Belarus, Moldova, Georgia, *Ukraine* and of course Russia,

This was of course many years ago. The events that led to the European countries in the former Soviet area of influence joining the EU are well-known. It was a necessary step, also to prevent nationalistic conflicts from breaking out in areas with peoples of different cultures, as had happened in the former Yugoslavia. The democratization of these regimes proceeded in fits and starts, with steps forward and back, but overall we can talk about a gradual pan-European pacification. Yet this process had clear political and military implications, because these countries entered the EU as a way of obtaining US

military protection from NATO - not the EU (which could not offer it, there being no European defence force). NATO’s expansion to the east thus took place without delivering the guarantees that Gorbachev had asked for when he negotiated German unification.

The relationship between the EU and Russia was initially regulated by the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (1994), which was ratified in 1997 and expired in 2007. Subsequently, in 2009, the EU signed the Eastern Partnership (EaP) with Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine, in order to increase cooperation with these countries, with a view to their eventual inclusion in the EU. Russia reacted by founding the Eurasian Economic Union (EEU) in 2010, which in 2011 became the Eurasian Custom Union (EACU). This union included Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Russia. In these initiatives, attention should be paid to the ambiguous position of Belarus, which is part of both the Eurocentric and the Russo-centric areas. Ukraine is in a similar position, albeit not formally, because of the Russian-speaking population in its south eastern provinces. So it came about that when the Ukrainian government posited joining the EU, Russia reacted by annexing Crimea. The Russian government wanted to draw a line to stop NATO expanding east. The EU, in turn, reacted with the only power it has: economic sanctions. The situation reached a stalemate.

In this scenario, any partial compromises, such as strengthening the EaP (Minzarari, Pistriniciu 2020), are destined to fail, if they do not consider the parallel problem of European security, which will persist as long as NATO retains its current set-up. The EU-Russia confrontation is also described as a confrontation between two different political communi-

ties: "A supranational organization with a normative agenda and a Westfalian state following power politics" (Marocchi 2017). This description is correct, but describes a deadlock with no evident solution. Any ambitious European foreign policy cannot accept a permanent deadlock.

The most convincing avenue remains that of the Common European Home, intuited by Gorbachev way back in 1987. The idea of a common home implies that peaceful relations are possible if all political subjects - from the Atlantic to the Urals - act fairly, without hegemonic aims. The European continent can become a free trade area where goods, people and capital move freely, without any national border becoming an insurmountable obstacle. Even if this does not lead to a common European citizenship in legal terms, the situation could be similar to the agreement between the EU and Switzerland. Ukraine could become the Switzerland of Central Europe.

The EU is like prey being fought over by two enemies, and it must take the initiative for a number of reasons, the first being that it intends to start building a European defence force. If Russia sees a European defence force as a further threat, strengthening the US-dominated NATO front, the situation will clearly degenerate. The second consideration is that the failure of the good neighbourhood approach, which has degenerated into a stand-off between two rival powers, is in part the responsibility of the EU too. If the EU had been able to guarantee the security of the candidate countries in Eastern Europe without NATO expanding to the east, Russia would probably have agreed to continue the peaceful cooperation process initiated after the fall of the Berlin Wall. On the thirtieth anniversary of this event, Gorbachev, in *Der Spiegel* (Nov. 8, 2019), declared: "after the end of Cold War, new

leaders failed to create a modern security architecture, especially in Europe. As a result, new dividing lines were created and NATO's eastward expansion shifted these lines to Russia's border". Lastly, in terms of security the international situation is further complicated due to the fact that a major new power, China, is rapidly increasing its conventional and nuclear potential.

The EU faces a difficult but not impossible challenge. NATO is experiencing something of an identity crisis. As the Atlantic alliance, it is tempted to become a global organization, thus dragging European countries into conflicts that could clash radically with their values and interests. The approach suggested by the idea of a common European home is an equal partnership between all participants, so - if we want to keep the name NATO - Russia should join with on the same footing as the US. But this solution is unlikely to please the US government. An alternative could be turning NATO into a sort of UN military agency, where, together with the EU (represented for now by France in the Security Council) Russia and China could decide whether to use UN forces for peace-enforcement in serious regional crises. Lastly, if the EU gets its own defence force, over time NATO may lose its importance for European security, NATO can be enlarged to Russia and transformed in an economic area for peaceful cooperation: for a proposal of *A Peaceful Cooperation Area from Vancouver to Vladivostok*, see: Baratta *et al.*, 2020.

EU and global governance

If the EU passively endures the crisis of the international order without reacting, the other world powers will easily be able to divide it into manageable dominions. The international system is witnessing the emergence of new players, like China, which have gained full indepen-

dence, both economic and military. In a multipolar world, where no single power can dominate, nationalism will inevitably guide the foreign policy of powers that are ambitious but lack a clear vision of the future.

Former superpower the US is now generating instability and insecurity. Its inconsistent reactions towards the old multilateral institutions when they become an obstacle to its immediate purposes - as happened with the WTO, the WHO and the International Criminal Court (ICC) - show that its foreign policy is not guided by any kind of reform plan. This lack of planning must be addressed rapidly, to prevent the system of international institutions being eroded still further. Interdependence has enabled all countries, both industrialized and emerging, to achieve a significant level of convergence and civil progress, though its fruits are poorly distributed.

If the EU equips itself with a federal budget and an independent defence system, it can begin to act on the world stage, not to assert its own hegemony, but to promote a new world order based on peaceful cooperation between industrialized and emerging countries. The EU must work to eliminate existing social imbalances and the threatened collapse of the biosphere, and ease military tensions between peoples who have become a community of destiny. The future of each nation depends on fair collaboration with others, not military clout. The EU is a union between national peoples who have rejected war as a way of solving the problems involved in interdependence. This is the message that Europeans can send to other peoples: "it is possible to coexist peacefully as citizens of the world".

Now let's take a look at the political projects that the EU could propose to the other inhabitants of the planet. Let's consider the WTO, the IMF and global private

finance, which today acts without any serious international constraints. The EU could convince a group of significant countries - a governance - to start building a new international order. When making these proposals (for a previous analysis: Montani 2019; Ch. 8), the idea of cosmopolitan citizenship remains on the back burner, because it cannot yet be translated into specific institutions. Global governance is only a necessary step towards that goal.

International trade - The US has questioned the WTO's Dispute Settlement Mechanism (DSM), opposing the replacement of outgoing judges. Thus the system of multilateral commercial relations is paralysed, because it has no body to resolve disputes. Although the US government's allegations are procedural in nature, it is clear that one of the criticisms concerns the independent judgment of the Appellate Body, which is accused of acting like a court. "The Appellate Body created itself as a judicial branch in a distant, even potentially contentious or oppositional, relationship with the WTO institutions" (Adinolfi 2019; 43). To understand the crisis of the WTO, we must remember that the DSM was introduced in Marrakesh in 1994, when the GATT (1947), founded on the principle of most favoured nation (MFN), and without an organ such as the DSM, became the WTO. The DSM enables member countries to settle their disputes by means of arbitrator decision, which after appeal, becomes executive. Yet since it was first created, growing problems have arisen due to complications resulting from the relationship between international trade and human rights, an inevitable intrusion. The GATT was able to function thanks to the fact that many member countries had the same degree of industrial and social development, while the WTO has had to deal with a convergence process between countries with different

degrees of economic and social development. "Human rights issues are constantly seeping into the working of the WTO. ... The WTO does not prevent members from protecting human rights, but its rules do constrain them" (Aaronson 2009). For example, some states have demanded respect for labour rights, gender equality and protection of child labour, and other states have rejected the expensive patents on medicines needed by poorer countries.

The WTO crisis recalls similar events that occurred during European integration. The Treaty for the European Economic Community (EEC) foresaw - after a transitional period - the accomplishment of the four freedoms: free movement of goods, services, capital and people. The EEC's Court of Justice (ECJ) played an important role. In the 1960s it issued some judgments on cases raised by judges in various countries which enabled it to establish the direct effect of European judgments in resolving cases, and the primacy of European laws over national ones. These judgments allowed the ECJ to defend the rights of European citizens in cases presented in national courts thanks to the fact that all the EEC countries had signed the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) approved in Rome in 1950. The principles of direct effect and the primacy of European laws over national ones could therefore not be called into question by either national governments or national constitutional courts.

A similar phenomenon can be identified on a global scale. In 1948 the UN approved the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), the importance of which grew in the following years, particularly after the decolonization process and the entry of new independent states into the UN. Since then, further agreements or treaties in defence of human rights have been approved, such as the International

Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), approved in 1966 and made executive in 1973. In recent years, the problem of global warming has sparked a series of UN initiatives in favour of sustainable development. Currently, national governments have committed to delivering the Global Development Goals by 2030. It is therefore no surprise that the WTO too is used for the defence of human rights. Yet the WTO cannot legislate on human rights. This is the grey area that is being challenged. The WTO is exploited by the defenders of human rights because the DSM's judgements become enforceable and can therefore also enforce respect for human rights, but only on the condition that the parties involved included this obligation in their trade contracts. One jurist rightly observed: "The human rights lawyer ... wants to be able to use trade law to enforce human rights simply because trade law enforcement is real and human rights enforcement, at least at the UN level, is not" (Green 2005: 237). This observation is crucial when it comes to understanding the improper use being made of the WTO to pursue human rights issues. Unlike in Europe, the International Court of Justice (ICJ) cannot accept cases concerning individual citizens, as article 34, 1 of its Statute tersely informs us: "Only states may be parties in cases before the Court". The WTO is an agency specialized in regulating international trade, and the ICJ cannot enforce respect for human rights, as the ECJ has been able to do.

At this point, differing opinions have emerged among jurists, as we can briefly summarise. The first, which can be deemed "realist", sees the WTO merely as a regulator of commercial treaties. "WTO law does not provide any hint that its provisions, even the most central ones, should be considered as international human rights. In fact, human rights is simply

a non-issue in WTO law” (von Bogdandy 2001; 656). The Appellate Body must only take into consideration the interests of the parties concerned, not the general interest, a supranational public good. “According to the Appellate Body, WTO law only serves its members and no further interest. The assumption of a ‘Community interest’ and a ‘Community common good’ is, in contrast, a core concept of European Union law ... and is among the most important argumentative tools in the ECJ’s jurisprudence” (von Bogdandy 2001; 661).

At the other end of the spectrum we have the progressive stance of Ernst-Ulrich Petersmann, who says: “Just as the ratification of the ECHR by all EC member states prompted the ECJ to construe EC law in conformity with the human rights guarantees of the ECHR, so must the law of worldwide organizations be interpreted in conformity with universally recognized human rights law” (Petersmann 2002; 623). Concluding his analysis, Petersmann recalls that the International Law Association recommended the creation of a parliamentary advisory committee and a representation of NGOs at the WTO and concludes: “The universal recognition of human rights, and the move from ‘negative integration’ to ‘positive integration’ and to worldwide rule-making in the WTO, call for further ‘constitutionalization’ of the WTO by means of more transparent rule-making procedures in the WTO, stricter parliamentary review, and the legal and judicial protection of human rights in the trade policy area” (Petersmann 2002; 647; Petersmann 2013).

The controversial relationship between international trade and human rights is far from being resolved, but the European Union can help show the steps that could be taken to ensure that the rights of citizens of the world are protected by world institutions too.

International money - In my aforementioned book, I discussed the dysfunctions and dangers of an international monetary system based on the dollar as the only reserve currency, and as a solution I proposed introducing an updated version of the Keynes Plan presented at Bretton Woods. Since then the state of the international payments system has deteriorated still further. One of the causes is political. The US government uses the dollar as a political weapon, to impose sanctions on enemy countries (e.g. Iran) preventing companies from using the system of payments in dollars towards “enemies”. These “enemies” therefore seek other currencies. In addition, the emergency measures taken by the states affected by the pandemic have caused a surge in public and private debt. Total debt (public and private) is estimated to have reached 255% of global GDP in 2019. In 2020 it will certainly exceed 300% of world GDP. This is a huge amount of money, which offers international finance opportunities to speculate on exchange rates, undermine overly indebted countries and destabilize the world economy.

This perilous situation calls for further reflections on the Keynes Plan, and in particular on its proposal for a world currency, the Bancor, managed by a “World Currency Union”. A modern Bancor already exists, the IMF’s Special Drawing Rights. The SDRs are based on a basket of currencies made up of dollars, euros, renmimbi, yen and sterling. To date the United States has always refused to allow the dollar to be replaced as an international currency by SDRs. Yet many economists argue that the time has come to strengthen and democratize the international monetary system, entrusting a group of countries with the responsibility for managing the world currency. José Antonio Ocampo, for example, says: “the IMF can use [SDRs] as an instru-

ment of international monetary policy in a global economic crisis. In 2009, for example, the IMF issued \$250 billion in SDRs to help combat the downturn, following a proposal by the G20. Most importantly, SDRs could also become the basic instrument to finance IMF programs. Until now, the Fund has relied mainly on quota (capital) increases and borrowing from member countries» (Ocampo 2019).

When the pandemic took hold, the UN Secretary General, Antonio Guterres, said: “Our strategy is to suppress Covid-19. And we can only suppress Covid-19 if all the countries have an articulated plan of action ... But ... it needs to be done in a coordinated way at the level of the G20 and then to mobilise ... I [estimate] about 2.5 to 3 trillion dollars to help the developing countries do the same. The IMF already has a lending capacity of about \$1 billion. We need special drawing rights (SDRs) and in a war economy we need to print money. The way to print money globally is through SDRs to put at the disposal of the developing world ...” (Guterres 2020). Guterres also proposes strengthening the World Health Organization to enable it to help poor countries without adequate health facilities, and refugee camps, where the virus could claim millions of lives.

All I need to add to these considerations is that the creation of a World Currency Union to manage a world currency would not only enable us to stabilize the world system of payments, but also to create a public budget for the UN to use, as the European Commission did recently with its proposal for strengthening the European budget to finance the “Next Generation EU” plan. The UN budget could be used to fund part of the Global Development Goals, to accelerate the convergence between rich and poor countries, to combat poverty effectively by funding social protection floors (SPFs) and for sus-

tainable development to implement the pledges made by national governments in Paris in 2015, which so far have remained “good intentions”.

International finance - We have seen how the creation of a world currency could lead to the creation of world public finance. Now let’s see how we could regulate the flows of international private finance, which generate imbalances and inequalities in the distribution of world income. Once again, for reasons of space, we cannot go into this in any great depth, so we will therefore focus on three issues: tax avoidance by businesses and individuals; tax competition between states, and citizenship for sale.

Globalization has increasingly integrated production chains around the world, but this process was only made possible due to the free international movement of capital. If capital can circulate, it is not surprising that companies and individuals try to pay taxes in countries where they are non-existent or very low. This is a phenomenon that the OECD calls base erosion and profit shifting. Some economists (Zucman 2015) calculate that the share of wealth tax evasion is 10% in Europe, 22% in Latin America, 30% in Africa, 52% in Russia and 57% in the Arab Gulf States.

The second issue concerns inter-state tax competition, a worldwide phenomenon that does not spare the countries of the European Union. Despite the solidarity constraints written in the Treaties, these countries seek to attract investment and private capital from other countries. In these cases, the notion of “national fiscal sovereignty” becomes meaningless. If an important country such as the US reduces tax rates on corporate profits and personal wealth, the rest of the world has to follow suit. This is a process that transfers public wealth (gained by progressive taxation) to private individuals, making it more difficult

for states with welfare systems to maintain their existing services, and prevent poor countries from starting their own public welfare systems.

Lastly there is the practice of citizenship for sale. The phenomenon started in the eighties, when a number of small Caribbean nations offered citizenship for sale to wealthy individuals, but it gradually spread and is now practised by many important countries, such as the US, Canada, the UK and also countries in the EU. The European situation is serious because Bulgaria, Cyprus, Malta, Hungary, Ireland, Luxembourg, Italy, Austria and Holland are not only selling their national citizenship but also, indirectly, European citizenship, granting businesses and individuals automatic access to free movement on the European market. In 2014, the European Parliament passed a resolution entitled "Citizenship is not for sale". But this has been ignored by national governments.

It is a practice that not only generates unjustified "rents" for national governments, but undermines the very foundations of democracy (Shachar 2020). What meaning is there in being a citizen of a certain nation or the EU, a political community, if others can simply buy the same opportunities to vote, reside and access social services? Furthermore, why grant citizenship for a fee to the rich and deny it to immigrants looking for work?

There is probably no single answer to the three problems I have outlined. But it can be useful to explore the idea of establishing a World Tax Authority (WTA) that would manage a world register of citizens' wealth and the consolidated profits of all multinational companies. After harmonizing rates, the overall amount of taxes collected could be distributed to individual national governments on the basis of the number of citizens living within their borders, and the national income produced.

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